

COVID-19 has set a milestone for RNA vaccines: a tool superior to conventional vaccines

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Although mRNA vaccines have undergone extensive preclinical and clinical investigations in the last decade mostly in the field of therapeutic vaccination against cancer, and several clinical studies have been ongoing for RNA vaccines against some infectious diseases, it is coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) that accelerated and enabled the first approval of an RNA vaccine, and thus has set a milestone for a powerful, elegant, alternative tool to conventional vaccines, a tool with far-reaching prospective.

RNA vaccines as fast universal vaccine formulation readily adjustable to new outbreaks

The recently approved 'Pfizer-BioNTech' and 'Moderna' vaccines against Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome Coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2), have demonstrated that RNA vaccines harbour the potential to build a simple, clean and fast universal vaccine formulation that can be easily adapted to evolving infectious diseases, enabling vaccine development in a time-range of weeks to few months, instead of years as has been so far the case for conventional vaccines.

The approved mRNA vaccines against COVID-19 are simply composed of mRNA encoding for the spike protein of SARS-CoV-2, encapsulated in lipid nanoparticles (LNPs) of ~80 nm diameter composed of 4 different types of lipids. The LNPs provide protection and delivery of the mRNA. The spike protein-encoding mRNA can be readily substituted for any other mRNA encoding for any antigen of interest: for example, encoding for any mutated spike protein; encoding for a protein of any other virus, bacterium or parasite, or for a mixtures of different mRNA sequences encoding for several antigens of interest. The same lipid formulation can be used to encapsulate any mRNA independent of its coding sequence (see the schematic illustration).

Once the sequence of the mRNA is designed, its production is an easy quick process, which takes approx. 2 days. The production is performed in completely cell- and virus-free *in vitro* system. The same established production process without any adjustment can be used to generate mRNA vaccines against any pathogen or mutated strains of interest.

Thus the mRNA vaccine allows rapid and dynamic responses to infectious disease outbreaks.

Figure shows the composition of LNP mRNA vaccine against COVID-19, and illustrating the adaptability of the vaccine by encapsulating mRNA encoding for any antigen of interest, such as mRNA encoding for any mutated target protein; mRNA encoding for a protein of any other virus, bacterium or parasite, or for a mixtures of different mRNA sequences encoding for several antigens of interest. (Illustration created by DR Hicham Bouabe)

COVID-19 RNA vaccines are by far the simplest and cleanest vaccine formulation

In contrast to conventional vaccines, such as whole pathogen containing vaccines, the approved mRNA vaccines don't contain viral or bacterial components (e.g. viral proteins and enzymes, viral genome, viral capsule), preservatives, (such as thimerosal, phenol, 2-phenoxyethanol), inactivating agents (e.g. formaldehyde), antibiotics, cellular residuals (e.g. yeast and egg proteins), gelatine, serum residuals (e.g. albumin), or adjuvants. The encapsulating lipids, and to some extent the mRNA itself, provide adjuvant activity. The only additives used to stabilize the Pfizer-BioNTech and Moderna COVID-19 RNA vaccines, are 'harmless' physiological salts (e.g. phosphate-buffered saline) and sugar (sucrose).

An additional superior advantage of mRNA vaccines is that they express only of the 'target' antigen, and subsequently induce only an adaptive immune response (antibody and T cell response) to the target antigen. In contrast, many conventional vaccines require, along with the target antigen, the co-expression of additional non-target proteins, against which antibodies and T cell response can be generated, with potential adverse impact. This is the case for example of adenoviral vector-based vaccines, and vaccines that use the 'molecular clamp' technology to stabilize the delivered antigen. The latter technique, when used to generate a COVID-19 vaccine (UQ-CSL V451) by the Australian University of Queensland in partnership with the company CSL, several trial participants returned false positive for the human immunodeficiency virus (HIV). This had the consequence that the Australian government abruptly terminated the purchasing agreement of UQ-CSL V451 COVID-19 vaccine. The false positive test results for HIV were due to the vaccination of the participants

with the spike protein of SARS-CoV-2 fused with a fragment of HIV-1 glycoprotein 41 (gp41). The participants generated antibodies also against the HIV protein fragment. Adenoviral vectors that are used as vehicle to deliver a target antigen of interest, induce robust antibody and T cell immune response to the adenoviral antigens, which can dominate over the immune response to the delivered target-antigen. In addition, pre-existing immunity against adenoviral vectors due to previous infections by multiple adenovirus types and/or previous vaccinations with adenoviral vaccines, often reduce the expression of and immunity to the target antigen delivered by adenoviral vectors, and might induce serious adverse effects.

Moreover, in comparison to attenuated whole vaccines and to some DNA vaccines, such as adenoviral vector-based vaccines, and in comparison to many natural viral infections, the vaccinated mRNA doesn't integrate into the genome of the cells. RNA needs to be converted into DNA, a reaction that requires a viral enzyme called reverse transcriptase, and the integration of converted viral DNA into the genome of host cells is usually mediated by viral enzyme called integrase. The mRNA vaccines don't include any of these viral enzymes. The vaccinated mRNA, its encapsulating lipids and the expressed viral antigen (in this case the spike protein of SARS-CoV-2) persist only transiently; they are entirely degraded within hours to few days, and thus no vaccine remnants will remain in the body. Only the vaccine-induced adaptive immune responses (antibody-producing B cells and T cells) persist and are ready to encounter any infection with SARS-CoV-2. This is so far the simplest, cleanest and elegant vaccine formulation that has ever been made.

Required improvements for RNA vaccines

Pfizer-BioNTech and Moderna COVID-19 vaccines can be considered as a first generation of approved RNA vaccines, which need to be followed by further RNA vaccine generations with improved properties. Some of the required improvements are discussed in the following.

Thermostable RNA vaccines for better logistic

One substantial shortcoming of the current LNP RNA vaccines is the required low storage temperature (at -60°C to -80°C for Pfizer-BioNTech vaccine, and at -20°C for Moderna's vaccine). This has a significant logistical disadvantage, in regards to shipping and storage, especially for very large vaccine doses. -20°C freezer, and especially -70°C freezer, are not standard equipment of all medical facilities even in western industrial countries; and many regions, especially in developing countries, lack almost completely a functional cold chain. CureVac, a German pharmaceutical company, has reported a SARS-CoV-2 mRNA vaccine (called CVnCoV), currently entering in phase 2b/3 clinical study, which has three-month thermostability at $+5^{\circ}\text{C}$. This is an encouraging improvement, however is not clear whether this higher thermostability is at cost of adding certain preservatives.

RNA vaccines that prevent not only the disease but also the transmission of the virus

Another disadvantage of the current COVID-19 RNA vaccines is the administration route, as they need to be injected intramuscular (IM).

IM vaccination doesn't induce mucosal immunity, of which hallmark the secretory antibody (immunoglobulin) isotype A, secretory IgA (sIgA). sIgA provides protection against viral replication and shedding within the mucosal surfaces of the respiratory/airway tract. Thus, although the current COVID-19 mRNA vaccines can prevent disease development, they are very likely unable to prevent the infection of vaccinated people and the persistence of the

virus in the nose and throat. This suggests that vaccinated people, although asymptomatic, may still be able to transmit live SARS-CoV-2 through respiratory droplets and aerosols. Thus, there is a need to develop a mRNA vaccine that can be administered intranasal, as this type of vaccine delivery induces mucosal immunity. In order to minimize possible adverse effects of intranasal vaccination, it can be performed as a second booster, few weeks after an IM injection of the same RNA vaccine.